

From Hong Kong to Sydney: The journey of the *Glamis Castle*, 1881

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Abstract

Over the first few months of 1881, following Chinese New Year, an unusually large number of Chinese migrants left Hong Kong for the Australasian colony of New South Wales. By the end of April, the Sydney press was reporting in alarmed tones that more than 2000 Chinese men had arrived in the city in the preceding few weeks, and that more were expected. Concerned by these unprecedented arrivals, the NSW government asked the Hong Kong government for information about these men and the ‘auspices’ under which they were leaving China for Australia. The resulting report noted that 4207 Chinese passengers, on eleven ships, had left Hong Kong for Australia in the first half of 1881, most of whom were destined for Sydney. Among the eleven ships was the *Glamis*

Castle, whose departure in late April was delayed while Hong Kong authorities inquired into the situation of its 840 Chinese passengers on behalf of the NSW government.

In this paper I will use the journey of the *Glamis Castle* in April–May 1881 to consider the colonial connections of Hong Kong and New South Wales. The latter colony had been connected to south China through the Canton trade from its beginnings as a British penal settlement in 1780s, and then to Hong Kong after its establishment as a Crown colony in the 1840s. From the mid-1850s, Hong Kong was also the port of origin of many thousands of Chinese men who came to New South Wales following the gold rushes. In this paper I will consider the journey of the *Glamis Castle* using Tony Ballantyne’s concept of the ‘horizontal’ connections of empire – the flows, exchanges and engagements that linked British colonies to each other – and explore the intertwined histories of empire and migration.

Slide 1: Title slide

Introduction

Slide 2: 'Punch's protest'

On the afternoon of Thursday, 26 May 1881, Smith's Wharf, at Miller's Point on Sydney Harbour, was crowded with people waiting for the arrival of the S.S. *Glamis Castle* from Hong Kong. News of the arrival of the ship had preceded her, as was usual, as news of her journey had arrived by telegraph from Hong Kong and from her earlier ports of call down the east coast of Australia. The *Glamis Castle* arrived in Sydney at a time of heightened agitation over the number of Chinese in the city, and in the colony of New South Wales more generally, and the *Evening News* reported that the city and water police had been 'mustered in strong forces' at the wharf in order to 'preserve order and aid Customs authorities in the discharge of their duties'. The reason this was seen as necessary was that on board the *Glamis Castle* were 820 Chinese passengers, at least a hundred more than any other single ship to date.

A month earlier, the New South Wales government had telegraphed to Hong Kong to inquire about the unprecedented number of Chinese passengers arriving in the colony over the early months of 1881, a situation that was resulting in increasingly alarmed articles, and cartoons

like this one, in the Sydney press. The resulting report from Hong Kong, sent in late June 1881, noted that 4207 Chinese passengers, on eleven ships, had left Hong Kong for Australia in the first half of 1881, most of whom were destined for Sydney. The departure of the *Glamis Castle* from Hong Kong in late April had been delayed so that Hong Kong authorities could specifically report on the situation of its many passengers.

This Hong Kong government report, including the investigation into the passengers of the *Glamis Castle*, and associated correspondence, can today be found in the New South Wales State Archives, in the correspondence of the Colonial Secretary; it can also be found in CO129, the Colonial Office records of correspondence with Hong Kong, and in abbreviated form in the Hong Kong *Government Gazette*. The report, which provides basic details of each passenger, together with a dozen or so longer accounts, provides a rare glimpse into a cohort of Cantonese migrants travelling to Australia through Hong Kong in the late nineteenth century.

Paper outline

Slide 3: Map showing NSW and HK

In my paper this morning, I want to use the story of the *Glamis Castle* to think about two things: the history of

Cantonese migration to New South Wales, and the history of intercolonial connections between New South Wales and Hong Kong. New South Wales was connected to south China through the Canton trade from its beginnings as a British penal colony in the 1780s, and then to Hong Kong after its establishment as a Crown colony in 1842. From the mid-1850s, Hong Kong was also the port of origin of tens of thousands of Cantonese, predominantly men, who came to New South Wales during and after the gold rushes.

While Australian historian Shirley Fitzgerald has written a little about the journey of the *Glamis Castle* in her 1997 history of the Chinese in Sydney, the story is not well known in the history of Chinese migration to Australia more generally, nor is it perhaps *that* significant – it was, after all, but one of hundreds of ship’s voyages between Hong Kong and the Australasian colonies over the course of the nineteenth century. But, as Canadian historian Renisa Mawani has noted in regard to her work on the *Komagata Maru*, ‘the ship ... provides a useful analytic frame to think outside and beyond the nation’ (Renisa Mawani, ‘Law and Migration Across the Pacific’, in *Within and Without the Nation*, p. 255).

A ship has a port of origin and a destination, which in the case of the *Glamis Castle* in 1881 were two British ports, two nodes in the complex network of connections that

linked together different places and peoples across the British Empire. My thinking about the journey of the *Glamis Castle* has been informed by New Zealand historian Tony Ballantyne's concept of the 'horizontal' connections of empire – of 'the flows, exchanges and engagements' that linked British colonies 'to each other as well as to Britain, the heart of the empire' (Tony Ballantyne, *Webs of Empire*, p. 14). The story of the *Glamis Castle*'s journey in April–May 1881 is, I think, emblematic of a larger history of intercolonial connections between Hong Kong and Australia, an intertwined history of empire and migration.

NSW and HK connections

Slide 4: 'Chinese life in Sydney'

The colony of New South Wales, which was established as a British penal settlement in January 1788, was connected to China from its very beginnings. Three of the ships that made up the 'First Fleet', the group of 11 convict ships whose passengers became Australia's first European colonists, were 'China ships' belonging to the British East India Company. After off-loading their cargo of convicts and soldiers, these ships continued on to Canton to take on cargoes of tea before they returned to England. Over the subsequent decades, the residents of New South Wales were reliant on the China trade for a range of goods, from

jars of preserved fruit and ginger, to umbrellas and camphorwood chests, to rice and tea. In return, goods such as seal skins, sandalwood, pearl shell and trepang were traded to Canton. Chinese men also arrived on these China ships – the earliest record we have is of a man called Ahuto, who arrived in 1803 and was still living in the colony two decades later. But until the late 1840s, these Chinese men were a small and scattered population among the predominantly English, Scots and Irish settlers.

The end of convict transportation to New South Wales in 1840, and the resulting need for a new colonial labour force, coincided with the establishment of British Hong Kong in 1842 and the forced opening of the treaty port cities, including Canton and Amoy. Chinese labourers were seen by members of the squattocracy – that is, by wealthy rural landholders – as a solution to their need for cheap labourer now that convict labour was no longer available. The first substantial shipment of Chinese indentured labourers, 121 men and boys, arrived from Amoy in 1848, and they were followed by about 3000 others over the next five years.

It was, however, with the discovery of gold in New South Wales and Victoria that the numbers of Chinese people arriving in the Australasian colonies increased most dramatically. Many of the Amoy labourers also absconded from their positions to join the gold rushes. By 1852, news

of the discovery of gold had reached Hong Kong, Canton and into the surrounding Pearl River Delta villages. In 1856, the first year that Chinese as a group were counted in the New South Wales Census, there were 1,800 Chinese men and 6 Chinese women in the colony. Five years later there were almost 13,000 men and 2 women, a number that was perhaps actually a significant undercount, with another official estimate putting the figure at 21,000. In 1881, when the *Glamis Castle* arrived in Sydney, the Chinese population of New South Wales was just over 10,000; 64 of whom were women. By this time, the population had diversified and was increasingly urbanised. Occupations included market gardeners, greengrocers, storekeepers and merchants, cabinet makers, herbalists and domestic servants, as well as a large number still involved in mining. They were almost all Cantonese who had arrived via Hong Kong.

Slide 5: Immigration statistics – Chinese to NSW

Over the 1850s, 60s and 70s, the patterns of Chinese migration to New South Wales were shaped by colonial laws aimed at restricting the entry and settlement of Chinese in the colonies. Victoria was the first colony to introduce an anti-Chinese immigration law in 1855, and New South Wales eventually followed suit in 1861. The 1861 Chinese Immigrants Regulation and Restriction Act, which came into force in 1862, introduced a £10 poll tax on

every Chinese entering the colony by land or sea and prohibited the naturalisation of Chinese settlers. Declining numbers of Chinese migrants led to its repeal in 1867, but new mining fields, including tin mining in the New England region in the north of the colony, and the introduction of anti-Chinese immigration legislation in Queensland in 1877, saw numbers of Chinese entering New South Wales rise again through the 1870s. As you can see from these statistics of Chinese coming and going from New South Wales, from 1878 the numbers of Chinese arriving in the colony start to substantially outnumber those leaving (although it's likely that more departed the colony than official statistics recorded, as many men quietly slipped across the border to Queensland).

Chinese arrivals in Sydney, early 1881

Although the rising numbers of Chinese arrivals were small, they triggered increasing anxiety in the British population, particularly in Sydney. As the capital and major port, Sydney received not only Chinese arriving from Hong Kong, but those drifting in from rural areas to either find new urban occupations or to eventually return home to China. Until the late 1870s, the number of Chinese living within Sydney itself was small – in 1861, only 189 out of 13,000 were recorded as living in the city. By 1878, however, the Chinese population of Sydney had risen to almost a

thousand, and the 1881 Census, taken in early April that year, found 1,321 Chinese present in the city. During the 1870s, a number of official inquiries in Sydney, including a Select Committee report on common lodging houses in 1876, had reported in dramatic tones on the apparent vice, squalor and immorality in the city's Chinese neighbourhoods. The increasing numbers of Chinese present in the city fuelled growing racist anti-Chinese sentiments and, in 1879, the New South Wales Premier, Sir Henry Parkes, began pushing for new anti-Chinese immigration legislation. Through Parkes' efforts, an Intercolonial Conference was held in Sydney in January 1881, where delegates from the Australasian colonies, including New Zealand but not Western Australia, agreed on the need for renewed restriction of Chinese immigration.

Slide 6: Arrivals statistics – dates, ships, no. of passengers

More than 2500 Chinese arrived in New South Wales from Hong Kong in 1880, and by April 1881 it was clear that this number was likely to be significantly greater that year. By mid-April, seven ships had brought around 2200 Chinese passengers to Sydney and more were known to be on their way. Furthermore, the ships leaving Hong Kong after Chinese New Year – those arriving in Sydney in April – had much larger numbers of Chinese passengers than earlier

arrivals. These figures were collated for the New South Wales government as part of a police inquiry into the Chinese arrivals undertaken in mid-April.

Slide 7: SMH article, 22 April 1881

There was substantial press coverage about the Chinese arrivals, some more balanced than others, and increasing popular disquiet about the 'great influx of Chinese' to the city. On 20 April 1881 the New South Wales government telegraphed to the Hong Kong authorities to inquire, as the *Sydney Morning Herald* put it, 'as to the reasons for this invasion'.

NSW's inquiry and HK's report

Slide 8: HK report (correspondence and printed), 22 June 1881

The Hong Kong authorities replied by telegraph to inform the New South Wales government that they were 'carefully watching the Chinese Emigration to Australia' and that further information would be transmitted. That further information came in the form a lengthy report, sent by Acting Colonial Secretary Frederick Stewart on 22 June 1881. His report included the investigation into the Chinese passengers on the *Glamis Castle*, copies of several local

Ordinances that outlined the powers of the Governor of Hong Kong with regard to Chinese emigration, correspondence about two earlier ships that ‘may also be of interest to the New South Wales government’, and finally a list of steamers that had left, or were preparing to leave, Hong Kong for the Australian colonies between January and June 1881.

Slide 9: Statistics of passengers departing HK for NSW

Passengers on the Glamis Castle

The passengers on the *Glamis Castle* were, according to the Hong Kong government investigation, all from the Pearl River Delta counties in Guangdong and they were all male. A report about the arrival of the ship in Sydney in the *Evening News* tantalisingly mentioned that there were ‘one or two females’ on board, including ‘a princess’ destined to be the wife of a well-to-do Sydney merchant, but if so these women were not apparently on board when the ship was inspected in Hong Kong. The Hong Kong report gave information about 810 passengers, listing details of their ticket number; name and surname; sex; profession, occupation or calling; native place, village and district; the port at which they were contracted to land; and finally, whether they were a free or hired emigrant. Using this

information, it is possible to get some broad pictures of who these migrants were.

Slide 10: Graph showing age of passengers

Slide 11: Map showing districts of origin

Slide 12: Graph showing districts of origin

Slide 13: Graph showing destinations by district of origin

Slide 14: Graph showing occupations by district of origin

The Hong Kong report also gave short accounts by ten passengers who were interviewed by Frederick Stewart, Acting Colonial Secretary, and John Gerrard, Acting Registrar General at the Harbour Office on the morning of 26 April 1881. Among those they interviewed were, for example, two passengers surnamed Lau from Lung To in Heung Shan.

Slide 15: Story of Lau A'In

The first of these was 12-year-old Lau A'In, who stated:

I am going to Sydney. I am a carpenter. My uncle is a carpenter in Sydney. I am going to my uncle. My father paid

my passage. It is my wish to go. I know I can do what I like, and go where I like. My father's name is LAU-KI. He lived in the Ú-cheung shop in Chung-wán. My father is not here with me just now, but my uncle is. He is going with me. I have not been enticed in any way. I shall have to pay nothing back for my passage. I expect \$7 a month. I have had no wages hitherto. I have been an apprentice.'

Slide 16: Story of Lau A-Fai

The second was Lau A-Fai, who stated:

I am 35 years of age. I am going to Sydney. I come from Lung-to in Héung-shán. I have paid \$42 for my passage. I pay it myself. I saved the money. I was once in Sydney before. I returned the year before last. I was 4 years there. I brought back \$300. I have given it to my wife. I have 3 children. I got my ticket at the Wo-tsán in Wo Hing Lane, Shéung-wán. I have been 4 or 5 days in the house. There are 24 or 25 of us there. I speak some English. I shall have nothing to pay for my passage.

Slide 17: 'Chinese joss house and camp at Vegetable Creek'

Around 650 Chinese landed from the *Glamis Castle* in Sydney, along with 400 tons of cargo, much of which was tea. Around 150 more went on with the ship to Melbourne,

arriving there on 5 June 1881. Those who landed in Sydney found themselves lodgings in Sydney's old Chinese quarter on Lower George Street, or in other parts of the city such as the Haymarket, but for most Sydney was not their final destination. Some were said to be going to work on market gardens in the suburbs, while others were going to make their way north to Queensland, where they hoped to be able to cross the border in secret to avoid paying Queensland's poll tax. Some were travelling further still, across the Tasman to New Zealand. The majority, though, were said to be headed to the tin mines of New England, to the mining centres of Tingha, Vegetable Creek and Inverell, where many of the earlier recent arrivals had joined the large numbers of Chinese already working there as tin miners.

1881 legislation

Slide 18: Influx of Chinese Restriction Act, NSW, 1881

The New South Wales Parliament had been debating the reintroduction of Chinese immigration restriction since 1879. Premier Sir Henry Parkes had introduced a bill into parliament in 1879, the Influx of Chinese Restriction Bill, which had passed through the Legislative Assembly but was rejected by the Legislative Council. Parkes did not let the matter rest, however, calling the Australasian colonies together in Sydney in January 1881 to discuss the question

of uniform action against Chinese immigration. As I mentioned earlier, all the colonies, including New Zealand but not Western Australia (which wanted to be able to import a Chinese labour force), agreed.

The events surrounding the successful introduction of the law in New South Wales is a longer story that I don't have time here to tell, except to mention that Parkes made use of the outbreak of smallpox in Sydney in mid-1881 to argue for the urgent restriction of immigration from China. In June he declared that Hong Kong and other Chinese ports were infected ports, with all ships coming from Hong Kong needing to go into lengthy quarantine (a matter that was the subject of stern correspondence from colonial authorities in Hong Kong as there was no outbreak of smallpox there). But, with the so-called 'Mongolian invasion' over the first half of 1881 as evidence, Parkes' 1881 bill was successful and *The Influx of Chinese Restriction Act* was granted royal assent on 6 December 1881.

Read the dot points off the slide:

- applied to 'any person of the Chinese race'
- £10 poll tax on each Chinese arriving by sea or land
- entry of Chinese by sea limited to one person for every 100 tons of shipping

- penalties could apply to ships' masters and to Chinese passengers
- exemptions for British subjects, 'bona fide' residents of NSW, Chinese government officials, crew

Slide 19: Immigration statistics – Chinese to NSW from 1881

The New South Wales 1881 Act was not particularly effective in reducing the numbers of Chinese arriving in the colony; it was difficult to administer and Chinese continued to move in and out of the colony as they had previously done. The exemption for naturalised British subjects also saw a dramatic rise in the numbers of Chinese applying for naturalisation, with 750 Chinese men naturalised in New South Wales in the five years from 1882 and 1887. Only 215 had been naturalised in the preceding decade and a half. The inefficiencies in the operation of the 1881 Act, together with increasing anxiety over the Chinese presence, prompted the New South Wales Parliament to introduce stronger restrictions in 1888. Over the 1880s, popular support for a white Australia had broadened and discrimination against the Chinese already in the colonies became much more accepted. The 1888 Act saw the poll tax increased to £100, the tonnage restriction increased to one Chinese passenger per 300 tons of shipping, and, once again, the prohibition of Chinese naturalisation. As you can

see here, immigration statistics for New South Wales clearly show the difference in the efficacy of the two Acts, and the Chinese population of New South Wales fell by more than 20 per cent between 1891 and 1901.

Conclusion

Slide 19: 'Passengers by a China tea steamer'

In my paper this morning I've suggested how we might consider the history of Chinese migration to Australia within the context of empire, bringing together histories of migration and intercolonial connection. As the beginning and end points of hundreds of ship's journeys, Hong Kong and Sydney were linked together through the movements of goods, and gold, and people, all part of the complex web of connections that stretched across the British Empire.

Historians of colonial Australia are used to thinking about imperial connections – most usually those with Britain and within Australasia – but the story of the *Glamis Castle* suggests, I think, the value in following some different routes through the history of the British Empire. In this case, the correspondence between Sydney and Hong Kong about the *Glamis Castle* has provided a rare glimpse into a group of Cantonese migrants for whom both ports were stepping stones in a journey between empires and between colonies.